

Physical Resources Utilization as ... (Adedeji, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686941>

Physical Resources Utilization as Correlates of Job Performance among Secondary School Teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated physical resources utilization as correlates of job performance among secondary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This study examined the extent to which the available physical plant, printed and non-printed resources are utilized in enhancing teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The research design adopted was a descriptive (survey) design. The population for this study comprised 1,976 teachers in the 158 public secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State (Field work, 2023) while the sample was 322 teachers using proportionate stratified and random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was an adapted Umeazor's (2019) questionnaire titled "Physical Resources Utilization and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire". The method used for analyzing the data was descriptive statistic of mean score. The findings of the study revealed that the extent of utilization of the available physical plant resources, printed resources and non-printed resources to enhance teachers' job performance was to a low extent with the mean scores of ($x = 2.11$); ($x = 2.02$); and ($x = 2.14$) respectively in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This study concluded that most of the physical resources are inadequately available and poorly utilized by teachers. This study concluded that most of the physical resources are inadequately available and poorly utilized by teachers. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended among others that the government and other stakeholders such as School Based Management Board (SBMC), Parent-Teachers Association (PTA) and other well-to-do individuals in the society should constantly up-grade, audit and maintain the available physical plant resources in secondary schools in order to ensure that they are properly utilized to influence positively the teachers' job performance.

Keywords: Physical Resources, Utilization, Job Performance, Availability

Introduction

Educational resources, be it human or material resource, play vital role in both the education system and instructional delivery in the classroom. The extent of acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitudes relevant to life altogether depends on the quality of teaching/learning activities that teachers provide for learners to interact with and the quality of the interaction; factors largely dependent on the nature and the quality of resources at the teacher's disposal (Umeazor, 2019). Such resources, if well used, increase the achievement level of the students and also engender positive changes. Educational resources have great significance in promoting administrative processes and likewise students' academic achievements (Amadi & Gbarador, 2021). For instance, the presence of material resources as part of educational resources in the school environment impacts greatly on teachers' job performance in the classroom. Teaching and learning cannot yield positive results without the teacher making use of some educational resources during classroom presentations. The level of teachers' job performance and their success in teaching various subjects in secondary schools is greatly dependent on the degree and extent of utilization of up-to-date education resources which revolve around facilities, equipment and supplies like the physical plants, printed and non-printed materials (Umeazor, 2019).

The availability and subsequent utilization of physical resources are vital to the excellence of students in school. The significance of physical resources in the success of secondary curriculum cannot therefore be over emphasized. The number of facilities that are available at a school determine the quality of education that is offered by the institution and in turn, it affects the performance of the students in examinations. World Bank (2018) established that the quality of an education system is dependent on the availability of certain key inputs which include; physical infrastructure, teachers and curricular. Societies and governments around the worlds should therefore strive to ensure that they improve their education systems by providing enough funding for key infrastructure in order to ensure that every child has an equal opportunity during the acquisition of the skills and knowledge that they require to lead productive and healthy lives. Physical resources form part of the external environment to learners which has been found to be associated with the quality of academic grades. Physical

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resources are comprised of facilities such as classrooms, dormitories, dining halls, playing fields, toilets, urinal pits, computer labs, schools halls, laboratories, offices and libraries among others (Umeazor, 2019). However, despite the fact that the availability of these resources is crucial to the learning process, their quality and effective utilization is equally important (OECD, 2018).

Education in most Sub-Saharan countries is faced chronic shortages in physical and human resources (Omego & Simatwa, 2015). Omego and Simatwa opined that rather than distributing the limited resources available for secondary education uniformly across schools, many governments allocate a relatively large share of available resources to a selected number of secondary schools. Similarly, findings by World Bank (2018) in a study on provision of textbooks and physical resources in secondary schools in sub-Saharan African countries: Botswana, Cameroon, Coted'vore, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Tanzania and Togo revealed that urban secondary schools have better textbook supplies and physical facilities than those in the rural areas. Dania. Obro, and Owzorhu, (2016) posited that inadequate instructional materials and poor utilization of physical and workshop facilities available for teaching has led to student failure and lack of competencies. Also, Dania. Obro, and Owzorhu noted that one of the problems in the Nigerian school system with regards to material resource management is not quite the non-availability or inadequate provision of good quality facilities but the inability to take good care of what is already available. Therefore, Dhakal (2020) affirmed that "the essential materials for teaching and learning are often unavailable in most of community secondary schools. The unavailability of such materials in secondary schools leads the teachers to talk and chalk in the teaching and learning". This means that without necessary material resources, teaching and learning will only become mechanical instead of interactive and this in the long run will affect teaching and learning outcomes.

Educational resources are of tremendous importance to the accomplishment of educational objectives and goals worldwide (Ajiboye, 2022) and teachxher' job performance. The performance of the teacher is often determined by the extent to which the outlined goals and objectives of the school are achieved as expected from the teacher (Onaolapo *et al.*, 2019). Teachers' job performance is central to all of the activities that are carried out in the school. The duties of the teacher in today's school system extend beyond the four walls of the classroom as they sometimes discharge their responsibilities even to the home front (Ayoro, Onyeike & Jack, 2023). Limon and Nartgun (2020) stated that job performance is the expected total value of what an employee is able to discharge in the line of duty. Amadi and Ezeugo (2019) highlighted that physical resources are very significant as they create conducive environment for teaching and learning; help the learners to develop skills through extra-curricular activities; motivate the school teachers in the execution of their duties; and help the retention of teachers through friendly teaching environment and good allowances among others. Therefore, principals who wish that their teachers do well need to also bear in mind that the materials used by the teachers must be regularly maintained to put them in good working condition and this is what obtains across different schools (Osuji &Iheanyichukwu, 2021).

A cursory look at the development of secondary schools in Zamfara State has shown that there are evidences of lapses in teachers' job performances (Umeazor, 2019). These lapses are mostly expressed through their negative behaviour and poor attitude towards work. Dania. Obro, and Owzorhu (2016) posited that inadequate instructional materials and poor utilization of physical and workshop facilities available for teaching has led to student failure and lack of competencies This also seems to have negative consequences on students' performances in both internal and external examinations as observed by the researcher. It was observed by the researcher that the issue of resource utilization as regards to the school physical plant facilities, printed and non-printed facilities in connection with teacher job performance in secondary schools in Zamfara State has become a new matter of discourse for researchers and likewise questionable. The current situation showcases that many of the teachers in Zamfara State secondary schools, whether rural or urban secondary school, are still teaching and working under very difficult conditions and poor working environment where many of these educational resources like the physical plants' resources, printed and non-printed resources are not properly utilized (Umeazor, 2019). With this devastating state, teachers find difficulties in performing their task and function efficiently and effectively.

Despite the Zamfara State government (past and present) efforts to support schools with educational resources in order to improve teachers' job performance as noted by the researcher, a lot are still at stake and the situation has not changed much. The problem concerning educational resources utilization for teacher job performance which has necessitated the present study therefore stands as the gap which must be filled. The present study sought to address the extent of educational resource(s) utilization for teacher job performance in secondary schools in Zamfara State, which is the problem of the study. It is against this background that this study is carried out to investigate the influence of physical resources utilization as correlates of job performance of secondary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area of Zamfara State, Nigeria.

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Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine physical resources utilization as correlates of job performance of secondary school teachers in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the:

1. extent to which utilization of the available physical plant resources enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.
2. extent of utilization of the available printed resources enhances teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.
3. extent of utilization of the available non-printed resources enhances teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are the available physical plant resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent are the available printed resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?
3. To what extent are the available non-printed resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested at α 0.05 level of significance in the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available physical plant resources and teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria
2. There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria
3. There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available non-printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was a descriptive (survey) design. This according to Adewale (2004) is an approach that looks for relationship on the basis of which projections are based. Also, it involves a planned collection of data over a large area for the purpose of making description. Thus, this method is considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to make careful record of what was observed so that the researcher can analyze the information obtained from a representative sample of the population and to describe situation as they exist (physical resources utilisation and teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria).

The population of this study comprised 1,976 teachers in the 158 public secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State. The sample size was made up of 322 teachers from secondary schools using proportionate stratified and random sampling techniques. The instrument used in gathering data for this study was an adapted questionnaire from Umeozor (2019). A structured questionnaire titled "Physical Resources Utilization and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (PRUATJQP)" which contained 21 items was used to collect data for the study. Items on the instrument were measured on a 4-point scale and rating as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SA). In order to ascertain that the instrument measured what it was expected to measure, the questionnaire was subjected to face validation by making the questionnaire available to three (3) experts in the fields of Educational Foundations and Measurement and Evaluation, Federal College of Education (Technical) Gusau for comments, criticisms and suggestions. Professional advice offered was adhered to before a final draft of the instrument was produced.

The reliability of the instrument was determined through a pilot-test. Copies of the questionnaire were administered on a sample of 30 teachers from three public secondary schools in Bungudu Local Government Area, Zamfara State. The Cronbach Alpha technique was used to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire which yielded coefficients 'r' value of 0.68, 0.60 and 0.64 for each of the three clusters, and an overall reliability 'r' value of 0.82.

Data collected and collated were quantitatively analyzed using the descriptive statistics of mean score, aggregate mean and standard deviation. The decision rule for the items on each of the research questions was based on the premise that any statement with a mean score of 2.50 and above was agree, while any one below 2.50 was disagree. The three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The decision rule

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was based upon that wherever p-value obtained or calculated value is greater than or equal to the alpha 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent are the available physical plant resources utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Scores of the Respondents Ratings on the Extent to which the Available Physical Plant Resources are Utilized for Teachers' Job Performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria (N= 322)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Staff rooms with adequate ventilation are utilized by teachers for consultations and timely give feedback to students	14	76	143	88	2.04	Disagree
2	Functional library stocked with up-to-date books are journals are utilized by teachers for their research consultations and private reading	21	58	171	72	2.08	Disagree
3	Technical workshop are utilized by teachers to teach basic technology practical for skill acquisition	31	60	163	68	2.17	Disagree
4	Functional guidance and counseling unit are utilized by teachers for consultations and to support students' academic growth	27	50	192	63	2.06	Disagree
5	Classrooms of 35-40 seating capacity with adequate space and ventilation are utilized by teachers to aid active teaching and students' participation in class	20	79	198	25	1.61	Disagree
6	Classroom furniture and fittings with cupboards/cabinets and shelves are utilized teachers to keep books and other materials in all the classrooms	29	71	189	33	2.30	Disagree
7	Computer room are used for students practical during computer class	20	14	186	102	1.85	Disagree
Grand Mean 2.02							

Fieldwork (2023)

Table 1 revealed the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the available physical plant resources are utilized to enhance teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The respondents disagreed to all the statements in Table 1 that the available staff rooms with adequate ventilation are utilized by teachers for consultations and timely give feedback to students ($x = 2.04$); that functional library stocked with up to date books are journals are utilized by teachers for their research consultations and private reading ($x = 2.08$); that technical workshop are utilized by teachers to teach basic technology practical for skill acquisition ($x = 2.17$) and that Functional guidance and counseling unit are utilized by teachers for consultations and to support students' academic growth ($x = 2.06$). Also, the respondents disagreed to the statements that classrooms of 35-40 seating capacity with adequate space and ventilation are utilized by teachers to aid active teaching and students' participation in class ($x = 1.61$); Classroom furniture and fittings with cupboards/cabinets and shelves are utilized teachers to keep books and other materials in all the classrooms ($x = 2.30$) and Computer room are used for students practical during computer class ($x = 1.85$). This implied that physical plant resources such as staff rooms, classrooms, workshops and furniture available were not adequate

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enough to enhance effective teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria with the grand mean of 2.02.

Research Question 2

To what extent are the available printed resources utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Scores and SD of the Respondents Ratings on the Extent to which the Available Printed Resources Utilized are Utilized for Teacher Job Performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria (N= 322)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Educative wall charts are pasted by teachers on the walls in the classrooms to promote learning in different subject areas	20	79	198	25	1.61	Disagree
2	Graphics for picture representation in teaching various subjects are displayed to support teaching	19	50	189	64	2.07	Disagree
3	Maps are used during geography teaching to support students' learning	19	34	189	80	2.18	Disagree
4	Work books are utilized by teachers in all subjects to give students assignment that will boost their cognitive and independent study	89	153	37	43	2.89	Agree
5	Posters and cartoons are used to support and display evidence of the lesson taught in the classrooms	27	50	192	63	2.06	Disagree
6	Up-to-date textbooks in the library with wider coverage in all subjects are used by teachers to promote research and teaching in varying context	23	37	181	81	2.01	Disagree
7	Pamphlets on past questions and answers available for different subjects	19	34	189	80	2.18	Disagree
Grand Mean = 2.14							

Fieldwork (2023)

Table 2 revealed the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the available printed resources are utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. Majority of the respondents agreed to only item 4 that workbooks are utilized by teachers in all subjects to give students assignment that will boost their cognitive and independent study with the mean score of 2.89. However, the respondents also disagreed to items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7 with the mean scores of 1.61, 2.07, 2.18, 2.06, 2.01, and 2.08 respectively. This implied that educative wall charts, dictionary, graphic pictures and maps were not available to enhance teachers' performance. Therefore, the grand mean of 2.14 was obtained and indicated that the available printed resources are utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent.

Research Question 3

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To what extent are the available non-printed resources utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria Zamfara State?

Table 3: Mean Scores and SD of the Respondents Ratings on the Extent to which the Available Non-printed Resources Utilized are Utilized for Teacher Job Performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria (N= 322)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean X	Decision
1	Laboratory tools and kits available for teaching physics practical	20	14	186	102	1.85	Disagree
2	Computers available for practical and research	30	34	187	71	2.07	Disagree
3	Public address system available in the classroom for presentations	19	50	189	64	2.07	Disagree
4	Chalkboard/whiteboard installed on the wall in all the classrooms	120	151	23	28	3.13	Agree
5	Internet facilities installed in the school for browsing and surfing of information from different websites	31	60	163	68	2.17	Disagree
6	Projectors available for teaching in different subjects	20	14	186	102	1.85	Disagree
7	Models/dioramas available for display in teaching various subjects in the classrooms	21	39	241	21	2.19	Disagree
Grand Mean = 2.01							

Fieldwork (2023)

Table 3 shows the perceptions of the respondents on the extent to which the available non-printed resources are utilized for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria Zamfara State, Nigeria. It was indicated as shown in the Table that Chalkboard/whiteboard were installed on the wall in all the classrooms with the mean score 3.13. On the other hand, majority of the respondents disagreed that laboratory tools and kits available for teaching physics practical with the mean score of 1.85, computers available for practical and research with the mean score of 2.07 and public address system available in the classroom for presentations with the mean score of 2.07. Also, the respondents disagreed to these statements that internet facilities installed in the school for browsing and surfing of information from different websites, that projectors available for teaching in different subjects and models/dioramas available for display in teaching various subjects in the classrooms with the mean scores of 2.17, 1.85 and 2.19 respectively. The grand mean of 2.01 was obtained and this implied that the what extent to which the available non-printed resources utilized teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was low.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available physical plant resources and teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria secondary schools in Gusau Local Government

Table 4: Significant relationship between utilization of the available physical plant resources for teachers' job performance secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Variables	Sample	Mean	Standard	t-cal	Degree of	STD	p-value	Decision
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	Size	Mean	Deviation	t-cal	Freedom	STD Error	p-value	Decision
Physical Resources	322	30.24	12.76	-8.594	321	.89851	0.00	Ho1 Rejected
Teachers' Job Performance		37.96	15.67					

Fieldwork (2023)

The result in Table 4 indicates that the calculated t-cal value is -8.594 and a p-value .000 with degree of freedom (d.f) 1193 at 5% (0.05) level of significance. Since the p-value .000 is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant relationship between utilization of available physical plant resources and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Table 5: Significant relationship between utilization of the available printed resources for teacher job performance secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Variables	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-cal	Degree of Freedom	STD Error	p-value	Decision
Printed resources	322	29.88	11.28	-3.194	321	.89851	0.01	Significant Difference
Teachers' Job Performance		32.28	12.86					

Fieldwork (2023)

The result in Table 5 indicates that the calculated t-cal value is -3.194 and a p-value of .001 with degree of freedom (df) 321 at 5% (0.05) level of significance. Since the p-value .001 is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the tested null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant there is a significant relationship between utilization of available printed resources for teacher job performance in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between utilization of the available non-printed resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Table 5: Significant relationship between utilization of the non-printed resources for teacher job performance secondary schools in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Variables	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-cal	Degree of Freedom	STD Error	p-value	Decision
Non-printed resources	322	26.52	12.39	-9.782	321	.89851	0.00	Significant Difference
Teachers' Job Performance		35.29	15.78					

Fieldwork (2023)

The result in Table 6 indicates that the calculated t-cal value is -9.782 and a p-value of .000 with degree of freedom (df) 321 at 5% (0.05) level of significance. Since the p-value .000 is less than the alpha level ($P < 0.05$), the tested null hypothesis is therefore, rejected. Thus, there is a significant there is a significant relationship between utilization of available non-printed resources for teacher job performance in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The first purpose of this study was to find out the extent to which utilization of the available physical resources to enhance teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The

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findings to this purpose revealed that the extent of utilization of the available physical plant resources for teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent ($x = 2.02$). Also, the hypothetical test indicated that a significant relationship was found in the mean ratings of teachers on the extent of utilization of available physical plant resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding concurs with Eze (2010) whose study reported that physical plant resources such as school building, library services and laboratories, among others as regards to teachers' utilization were lacking in the schools. This was the major factor that affected students' academic learning and teacher effectiveness in schools. Unavailability of school health services, school fence and provision of power supply were also important variables that affected teachers' job performance (Eze, 2010). Atieno (2014) also confirmed that physical plant facilities in the schools were overstretched and thus affected quality education in the schools. Whereby the physical plant resources were not effectively utilized by the teachers in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, and such situation will affect teacher job performance and has negative consequences on accomplishment of instructional task and students' academic achievements will be put in jeopardy in school.

The second purpose of this study was to find out the extent to which utilization of the available printed resources to enhance teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The finding of the study also discovered that the extent of teachers' utilization of the available printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent ($x = 2.11$). The hypothetical test showed that a significant difference was found between the mean ratings of teachers on the extent of utilization of available printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding concurs and corresponds with the finding of Adebule and Ayoola (2014) who affirmed that instructional materials were found in schools to an extent; however, teachers were not putting the materials into good use in teaching of some subjects. Stephen (2011) finding showed that there was low frequency in teachers' use of the available resource materials. Andambi and Kariuki (2013) reported that the most commonly available printed resources used for teaching were textbooks, charts, maps, teacher made materials and newspapers; however, teachers were not using them for teaching and learning. Whereby the printed resources are not effectively utilized by the teachers in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, and this situation will continually affect teacher job performance. This situation has negative consequences on instructional goal accomplishment and stands to jeopardize students' academic achievements in school. Kimeu, Tanui and Ronoh (2015) also observed that both teachers' and students' academic performances depended on teachers' utilization of printed resources.

The third purpose of this study was to find out the extent to which utilization of the available printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The findings of the study further discovered that the extent of teachers' utilization of the available non-printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria was to a low extent ($x = 2.01$). The finding discovered that in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, computers available for practical and research and television set available for teaching in different subjects among other non-printed resources were both utilized to a low extent. The hypothetical test showed that a significant relationship was found between the mean ratings of teachers on the extent of utilization of available non-printed resources for teacher job performance in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

This finding concurs and is in line with Kimeu, Tani and Ronoh (2015) whose study found that students' academic performance depended on use of non-printed teaching and learning materials like the chalkboard, laboratory apparatus and chemicals, among others, but teachers were not making adequate use of them. Ntui and Udah (2015) found in secondary schools in Calabar, Cross Rivers State, Nigeria, that teachers were not making use of the audio-visual materials in the schools. A significant difference was observed in the schools concerning teachers' utilization of non-printed resources. Andambi and Kariuki (2013) also confirmed that radio was the most commonly available non-printed resources in the schools, but teachers were not using them for teaching and learning. Whereby the non-printed resources are not effectively utilized by the teachers in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria, and this situation will continually affect teacher job performance. This situation has negative consequences on instructional goal accomplishment and stands to jeopardize students' academic achievements in school. Ugwuanyi (2013) reported that no meaningful learning or transfer of what has been learned will take place if such learning occurs in a situation devoid of relevant non-printed materials and activities as well as concrete experiences – given through teacher job performance.

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Conclusion

Educational resources be it physical plant resources, printed resources or non-printed resources are very vital for effective teacher job performance. In Zamfara State, most of the physical resources are inadequately available and poorly utilized by teachers to a low extent for their job performance, while a huge number of these resources are unavailable to a high extent in secondary schools of Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State. Failure for secondary school teachers to deliver their lessons effectively in the classroom has negative consequences on both schools' development and students' academic achievement. The situation in Zamfara State calls for absolute redress in order to impact positively on teacher job performance through resource utilization.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made that:

1. The Zamfara State government and other stakeholders such as School Based Management Board (SBMC), Parent-Teachers Association (PTA) and other well-to-do individuals in the society should constantly up-grade, audit and maintain the available physical plant resources in secondary schools in order to ensure that they are properly utilized to influence positively the teachers' job performance.
2. Secondary schools' principals should ensure that they encourage teachers to utilize properly the available printed resources for their job performance in secondary schools. They should not only improvise the printed resources but also supervise teachers to ensure their effective utilization during instructional delivery in the classroom.
3. The principals should also apply appropriate maintenance culture in order to protect the available non-printed resources for effective teacher job performance in secondary schools. Constant training and retraining should be given to teachers in order to improve utilization of the non-printed educational resources in the schools.

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